

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Release Notes (for PIC users)

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Approval

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Release Note		
Issue 1	Revision 0	Signature
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1. Introduction

The PLATO Input Catalogue (PIC) is a composite product and includes 6 tables and 2 documents. Each PIC includes only targets which fall within a given PLATO observed field.

The LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv catalog is defined for the first PLATO Long Observation Phase (LOP) named LOPS2.

The LOPS2 field centre in Equatorial (ICRS) coordinates is:

RA = 95.31043 (deg)

DEC = - 47.88693 (deg)

The LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv catalog data are made public by ESA for the first PLATO Guest Observer (GO) call.

The main table is the target table, which is composed by four lists (called subPICs):

- tPIC: core science stars (P1, P2, P4, P5) and stars with confirmed/candidate planet(s)
- fgPIC: Fine Guidance System (FGS) stars used to guarantee the attitude of the spacecraft
- cPIC: instrument calibration stars to perform some of the calibration steps on the basis of the full-frame CCD images and imagerettes acquired at the beginning of each calibration phase
- scvPIC: calibration and validation stars for both stellar and exoplanets science

In addition, each subPIC contains subSamples.

The four subPICs are merged to build a single target table. The targets that belong to more than one subPIC, or to more than one subSample within a subPIC, are included only once in the PIC (i.e. the PIC targets are not repeated).

The 6 tables included in PIC2.2.0.1 are:

- LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv
- LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The two EPIC tables contain all sources as defined in the corresponding PIC target and contaminants tables. However, they include only a subset of the columns i.e. those needed by the Science Operation Center (hereafter SOC).

2. Scope and Purpose

This note is the reference document for the delivery of the first public release of the PLATO Input Catalogue for LOPS2.

The PLATO Input Catalogue naming convention is briefly summarized here:

XXXXXPICN1.N2.N3.N4-t(-fg)(-c)(-scv)

where:

- XXXXX = observed field identifier (in this case: LOPS2)
- N1.N2.N3.N4 = PIC release version (here 2.2.0.1)
- t = tPIC is included
- fg = fgPIC is included
- c = cPIC is included
- scv = scvPIC is included

The scope of this note is to describe the content of the tables included in the LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 release:

- **LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1**: it is the main PIC table, and contains all targets including scientific targets, FGS Performance stars, instrument calibration stars and science calibration and validation stars. The PICtarget table contains astrometric, photometric and astrophysical characterization for all stars and NSR values for tPIC and scvPIC targets.
- **LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSouceld2.2.0.1**: contains, for each object in the PICtarget table, the source identifiers from catalogues and/or surveys relevant for a given PIC target during the PIC implementation. This additional souceld table is meant to include only the identifiers from catalogues that were used for the selection and/or characterisation of a given source.
- **LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1**: contains the list of photometric contaminants. All contaminants within a field (with margins) are listed. Each contaminant is listed only once. All targets are also included in the contaminant table.
- **LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSouceld2.2.0.1**: contains, for each object in the PICcontaminant table, the source identifiers from catalogues and/or surveys relevant for the PIC implementation. This additional souceld table is meant to include only the identifiers from catalogues that were used for the selection and/or characterisation of a given contaminant.

- **LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1:** contains, for each target, only the information needed by SOC
- **LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1:** contains, for each contaminant, only the information needed by SOC

For each table in the release, the data model is described in the accompanying document LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Data Definition, which includes more details on each PIC column.

3. LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The PICtarget table includes **289253** distinct targets.

The target distribution in the four subPICs and for each subsample in a given subPIC is illustrated in the following table.

tPIC		fgPIC		cPIC		scvPIC	
Sample	# targets	Sample	# targets	Sample	# targets	Sample	# targets
All	217741	All	2640	All	71671	All	38585
P1	12900	F-CAM blue	1801	R1 F-CAM	547	SCV1a	849
P2	868	F-CAM red	2174	R2 F-CAM	17800	SCV1b	1539
P4	15037			R3 F-CAM	547	SCV1c	806
P5	189415			R4 F-CAM	547	SCV1d	1
Planet host	789			R5 F-CAM	17800	SCV1e	53
Prime sample	17101			R1 N-CAM	10532	SCV2a	50
Proprietary sample	0			R2 N-CAM	62639	SCV2b	306
Color sample	0			R3 N-CAM	10532	SCV3a	54
				R4 N-CAM	10532	SCV3b	173
				R5 N-CAM	62639	SCV4a	233
						SCV4b	1592
						SCV5	4854
						SCV6	6
						SCV4c	28175

The number of sources in common among different subPICs are reported in the following table:

	tPIC	fgPIC	cPIC	scvPIC
tPIC	217741	386	33049	2696
fgPIC	386	2640	2062	343
cPIC	33049	2062	71671	4327
scvPIC	2696	343	4327	38585

3.1 LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv statistics

Definition of the provided statistics:

Mean	Mean of the valid entries
SD	Standard Deviation of the valid entries
Minimum	Minimum of valid entries
Maximum	Maximum of valid entries
nValid	Number of valid entries (not null)
nNull	Number of null entries
%nValid	Percentage of valid entries (not null)
%nNull	Percentage of null entries
bitmaskValid	Number of valid entries (not zero)
bitmaskEmpty	Number of empty entries (zero)
Q10	Value below which 10% of entries fall (10th percentile)
Median	Value below which 50% of entries fall
Q90	Value below which 90% of entries fall (90th percentile)

Please note that for bitmasks when no value is available (empty), the bitmask is set to zero, while for all other columns when no value is available, the column is set to null.

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The relevant statistics for all the columns in LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1 table are reported in the following table:

Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
PICid					289253	0	100.0	0.0					
PICname					289253	0	100.0	0.0					
StarName					289253	0	100.0	0.0					
RAdeg	101.36	21.72	47.14	143.52	289253	0	100.0	0.0			69.94	103.63	128.92
eRAdeg	0.31	0.71	0.06	76.34	289253	0	100.0	0.0			0.12	0.16	0.44
DEdeg	-44.45	13.89	-77.77	-17.9	289253	0	100.0	0.0			-63.92	-43.89	-26.19
eDEdeg	0.33	0.78	0.1	83.01	289253	0	100.0	0.0			0.13	0.17	0.47
pmRA	-0.8	25.98	-1172.19	6491.22	289200	53	99.98	0.02			-14.63	-1.74	13.42
epmRA	0.02	0.05	0.01	2.06	289200	53	99.98	0.02			0.01	0.01	0.04
pmDE	5.2	32.02	-5708.61	1707.7	289200	53	99.98	0.02			-14.05	4.59	24.84
epmDE	0.03	0.06	0.01	2.24	289200	53	99.98	0.02			0.01	0.01	0.04
pm	20.42	36.21	0.03	8644.32	289200	53	99.98	0.02			3.59	11.97	42.12
epm	0.0	0.03	0.0	5.02	289200	53	99.98	0.02			0.0	0.0	0.0
Plx	2.73	3.51	-3.45	272.16	289200	53	99.98	0.02			0.6	1.84	5.43
ePlx	0.02	0.05	0.01	2.24	289200	53	99.98	0.02			0.01	0.01	0.03
distance	791.8	1226.4	3.67	50273.3	289200	53	99.98	0.02			183.54	538.87	1640.07
edistance	28.23	274.71	0.0	26911.7	289200	53	99.98	0.02			0.53	4.02	39.81
Glon	255.63	15.74	222.6	289.26	289253	0	100.0	0.0			234.41	255.4	277.32
Glat	-19.52	13.8	-54.59	5.37	289253	0	100.0	0.0			-39.88	-17.68	-2.62

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Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
posEpoch			2016.0	2028.3	289253	0	100.0	0.0					
refEpoch			1991.25	2016.0	289253	0	100.0	0.0					
posPropFlag			0	2	289253	0	100.0	0.0					
PlatoMagNCAM	11.63	1.28	1.78	19.98	289253	0	100.0	0.0			9.96	11.89	12.63
ePlatoMagNCAM	0.02	0.02	0.0	0.6	289253	0	100.0	0.0			0.01	0.01	0.04
PlatoMagFCAMb	11.96	1.33	2.08	21.61	289253	0	100.0	0.0			10.3	12.17	12.88
ePlatoMagFCAMb	0.02	0.03	0.0	1.55	289253	0	100.0	0.0			0.01	0.01	0.04
PlatoMagFCAMr	11.31	1.28	1.45	19.26	289253	0	100.0	0.0			9.62	11.6	12.37
ePlatoMagFCAMr	0.01	0.02	0.0	0.98	289253	0	100.0	0.0			0.0	0.01	0.03
Gmag	11.9	1.29	2.07	20.42	289252	1	100.0	0.0			10.23	12.15	12.86
eGmag	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.04	289252	1	100.0	0.0			0.0	0.0	0.0
BPmag	12.33	1.35	2.94	21.74	289251	2	100.0	0.0			10.68	12.51	13.4
eBPmag	0.0	0.01	0.0	0.86	289251	2	100.0	0.0			0.0	0.0	0.0
RPmag	11.31	1.28	1.54	18.97	289251	2	100.0	0.0			9.63	11.61	12.38
eRPmag	0.0	0.01	0.0	0.87	289251	2	100.0	0.0			0.0	0.0	0.0
Hpmag	9.17	1.46	6.83	12.51	11	289242	0.0	100.0			7.34	9.55	9.77
eHpmag	0.02	0.05	0.0	0.17	11	289242	0.0	100.0			0.0	0.0	0.0
Ksmag	11.02	0.82	4.17	12.44	14579	274674	5.04	94.96			9.95	11.2	11.88
eKsmag	0.02	0.08	0.02	10.0	14579	274674	5.04	94.96			0.02	0.02	0.03
AG	0.08	0.14	0.0	2.82	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.01	0.03	0.17

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Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
eAG	0.01	0.02	0.0	0.43	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.0	0.01	0.03
AKs	0.01	0.02	0.0	0.32	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.0	0.0	0.02
eAKs	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.05	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.0	0.0	0.0
EBPRP	0.04	0.07	0.0	1.43	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.0	0.01	0.08
eEBPRP	0.01	0.01	0.0	0.23	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.0	0.0	0.01
extStatus			0	1	289253	0	100.0	0.0					
VmagCalculated	12.16	1.33	2.28	21.92	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			10.52	12.34	13.16
eVmagCalculated	0.02	0.03	0.0	0.76	288006	1247	99.57	0.43			0.01	0.01	0.05
Teff	5685.19	929.78	2150.0	50000.0	256046	33207	88.52	11.48			4700.5	5836.3	6431.16
eTeff	175.98	71.82	0.02	5934.8	256036	33217	88.52	11.48			17.25	196.5	224.75
Radius	3.05	6.14	0.01	174.94	254989	34264	88.15	11.85			0.83	1.56	7.7
eRadius	0.16	0.33	0.0	26.88	254969	34284	88.15	11.85			0.07	0.11	0.27
Mass	1.39	0.67	0.04	8.41	254602	34651	88.02	11.98			0.86	1.25	2.4
eMass	0.1	0.05	0.01	1.2	254599	34654	88.02	11.98			0.05	0.1	0.13
CaseFlag			1	21	289253	0	100.0	0.0					
PICmainSourceFlagBOL									289253	0			
tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL									217741	71512			
fgPICsourceFlag									2640	286613			
cPICsourceFlag									71671	217582			
scvPICsourceFlag									38585	250668			

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Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
NSSflag									42737	246516			
qualityFlag									289252	1			
tPICplanetFlag									789	288464			
fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag			1	2	72249	217004	24.98	75.02					
targetStatusFlag									0	289253			
BOLrandomNSRNCAM_T	163.39	433.21	1.51	140400.0	253630	35623	87.68	12.32			54.28	128.2	237.8
BOLrandomSysNSRNCAM_T	163.81	433.14	9.18	140400.0	253630	35623	87.68	12.32			55.03	128.5	238.0
BOLnCameraObsNCAM_T			0	24	253630	35623	87.68	12.32					
BOLnCameraSatNCAM_T			0	24	253630	35623	87.68	12.32					
EOLrandomNSRNCAM_R	265.36	766.19	1.71	222100.0	253630	35623	87.68	12.32			70.12	190.4	384.4
EOLrandomSysNSRNCAM_R	265.67	766.14	9.26	222100.0	253630	35623	87.68	12.32			70.71	190.6	384.5
EOLnCameraObsNCAM_R			0	22	253630	35623	87.68	12.32					
EOLnCameraSatNCAM_R			0	22	253630	35623	87.68	12.32					
tPICscientificRanking	0.01	0.06	0.0	1.0	217741	71512	75.28	24.72			0.0	0.0	0.01
scvPICscientificRanking			1	3	38585	250668	13.34	86.66					
scientificPriority					0	289253	0.0	100.0					
scheduledTarget					0	289253	0.0	100.0					

The column **posPropFlag** is a flag indicating if and how the positions of the targets were propagated from refEpoch to posEpoch.

The occurrences for the values of column posPropFlag are reported in the following table:

posPropFlag value	number of targets
0	53
1	289189
2	11

The column **caseFlag** is an integer flag which gives the basic information on the inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes for the targets and the contaminants in both FCAM and NCAM. In the LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1 table not all possible caseFlag values are present. In the following table we include the occurrences for each of the caseFlag values present in the table:

caseFlag value	number of targets
1	205381
2	15086
3	3965
4	63574
5	1054
6	138
7	1
13	1
21	53

The column **PICmainSourceFlagBOL** is a bitmask indicating to which subPIC an object belongs to and if it is part of the prime and/or proprietary sample. The occurrences of the possible bits in column PICmainSourceFlagBOL are listed in the following table:

PICmainSourceFlagBOL bit	number of targets
0000000 ₂ = 0	0
0000001 ₂ = 1	17101
0000010 ₂ = 2	0
0000100 ₂ = 4	217741
0001000 ₂ = 8	2640
0010000 ₂ = 16	71671
0100000 ₂ = 32	38585
1000000 ₂ = 64	0

The column **tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL** is a bitmask indicating to which tPIC sample an object belongs to, when the NSR is calculated at BOL.

The occurrences of the possible bits in column tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL are listed in the following table:

tPICsourceFlagNCAM_BOL bit	number of targets
0000000 ₂ = 0	71512
0000001 ₂ = 1	12900
0000010 ₂ = 2	868
0000100 ₂ = 4	189415
0001000 ₂ = 8	15037
0010000 ₂ = 16	789
0100000 ₂ = 32	17101
1000000 ₂ = 64	0

The column **fgPICsourceFlag** is a bitmask indicating to which fgPIC sample an object belongs to. The occurrences of the possible bits in column fgPICsourceFlag are listed in the following table:

fgPICsourceFlag bit	number of targets
$00_2 = 0$	286613
$01_2 = 1$	1801
$10_2 = 2$	2174

The column **cPICsourceFlag** is a bitmask indicating to which cPIC sample an object belongs to. The occurrences of the possible bits in column cPICsourceFlag are listed in the following table:

cPICsourceFlag bit	number of targets
$000000000_2 = 0$	217582
$000000001_2 = 1$	547
$000000010_2 = 2$	17800
$000000100_2 = 4$	547
$000001000_2 = 8$	547
$000010000_2 = 16$	17800
$000100000_2 = 32$	10532
$001000000_2 = 64$	62639
$001000000_2 = 128$	10532
$010000000_2 = 256$	10532
$100000000_2 = 512$	62639

The column **scvPICsourceFlag** is a bitmask indicating to which scvPIC sample an object belongs to. The occurrences of the possible bits in column scvPICsourceFlag are listed in the following table:

scvPICsourceFlag bit	number of targets
000000000000 ₂ = 0	250668
0000000000001 ₂ = 1	849
0000000000010 ₂ = 2	1539
0000000000100 ₂ = 4	806
0000000001000 ₂ = 8	1
0000000010000 ₂ = 16	53
0000000100000 ₂ = 32	50
0000001000000 ₂ = 64	306
0000010000000 ₂ = 128	54
0000100000000 ₂ = 256	173
0001000000000 ₂ = 512	233
0010000000000 ₂ = 1024	1592
0100000000000 ₂ = 2048	4854
0100000000000 ₂ = 4096	6
1000000000000 ₂ = 8192	28175

The column **NSSflag** is a bitmask indicating the presence of binary/multiple stellar system (NSS = non-single star). The occurrences of the possible bits in column NSSflag are listed in the following table:

NSSflag bit	number of targets
000000 ₂ = 0	246516
000001 ₂ = 1	42737
000010 ₂ = 2	19753
000100 ₂ = 4	1592
001000 ₂ = 8	14065

NSSflag bit	number of targets
010000 ₂ = 16	13675

The column **qualityFlag** is a bitmask containing indicators for issues in Gaia astrometry and photometry. The occurrences of the possible bits in column qualityFlag are listed in the following table:

qualityFlag bit	number of target
0000000000 ₂ = 0	1
0000000001 ₂ = 1	0
0000000010 ₂ = 2	17296
0000000100 ₂ = 4	13843
0000001000 ₂ = 8	2142
0000010000 ₂ = 16	852
0000100000 ₂ = 32	39721
0001000000 ₂ = 64	15444
0010000000 ₂ = 128	3473
0100000000 ₂ = 256	59
1000000000 ₂ = 512	230073

The column **tPICPlanetFlag** is a bitmask indicating the presence of at least a confirmed planet and/or a candidate planet separated according to their discovery method. The occurrences of the possible bits in column tPICplanetFlag are listed in the following table:

tPICplanetFlag bit	number of target
000000000000 ₂ = 0	288464
000000000001 ₂ = 1	102
000000000010 ₂ = 2	582
000000000100 ₂ = 4	58
000000001000 ₂ = 8	9

tPICplanetFlag bit	number of target
00000010000 ₂ = 16	31
00000100000 ₂ = 32	4
00001000000 ₂ = 64	3
00010000000 ₂ = 128	11
00100000000 ₂ = 256	6
01000000000 ₂ = 512	3
10000000000 ₂ = 1024	0
10000000000 ₂ = 2048	1

For targets in fgPIC and cPIC is important to know if they are variable. The column **fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag** is set for those targets. The occurrences of the values of column **fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag** are listed in the following table:

fgPICcPICvariabilityFlag value	number of targets
1	3853
2	68396

The column **scvPICscientificRanking** is an integer flag indicating the priority of the scvPIC target. The occurrences for the values of column **scvPICscientificRanking** are reported in the following table:

scvPICscientificRanking value	number of targets
1	27117
2	9840
3	1628

3.2 LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv histograms

4. LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1 table contains, for each object in the LOPS2PICtarget2.2.0.1 table, the source identifiers from catalogues and/or surveys relevant for a given PIC target during the PIC implementation. This additional sourceId table is meant to include the identifiers from catalogues that were used for the selection and/or characterisation of a given source.

4.1 LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv statistics

The relevant statistics for all the columns in LOPS2PICtargetAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1 table are listed in the following table:

name	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull
PICId	289253	0	100.0	0.0
GaiaSourceId	289252	1	100.0	0.0
Hipparcos2SourceId	10	289243	0.0	100.0
HipparcosDMSourceId	1	289252	0.0	100.0

name	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull
2MASSPSCsourceId	14579	274674	4.04	95.96
eu_hostname	211	289042	0.07	99.93
nasaps_hostname	148	289105	0.05	99.95
nasatoj_toipfx	682	288571	0.24	99.76
nasatoj_tid	682	288571	0.24	99.76
oec_hostname	134	289119	0.05	99.95

5. LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1 table contains the list of photometric contaminants. Most contaminants are selected from the Gaia DR3 catalogue. Gaia has been complemented at the bright end using the Hipparcos2, Hipparcos DM (*annex 1*), Tycho2 and TDSC catalogues.

Galactic coordinates

5.1 LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv statistics

Definition of the provided statistics:

Mean	Mean of the valid entries
SD	Standard Deviation of the valid entries
Minimum	Minimum of valid entries
Maximum	Maximum of valid entries
nValid	Number of valid entries (not null)
nNull	Number of null entries
%nValid	Percentage of valid entries (not null)
%nNull	Percentage of null entries
bitmaskValid	Number of valid entries (not zero)
bitmaskEmpty	Number of empty entries (zero)
Q10	Value below which 10% of entries fall (10th percentile)
Median	Value below which 50% of entries fall
Q90	Value below which 90% of entries fall (90th percentile)

Please note that for bitmasks when no value is available (empty), the bitmask is set to zero, while for all other columns when no value is available, the column is set to null.

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The relevant statistics for all the columns in LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1 table are listed in the following table:

Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
PICcontaminantId					105865176	0	100.0	0.0					
PICcontaminantName					105865176	0	100.0	0.0					
StarName					105865176	0	100.0	0.0					
RAdeg	108.12	21.75	47.1	143.52	105865176	0	100.0	0.0			77.4	112.52	135.16
eRAdeg	5.06	5.63	0.02	130.7	105865176	0	100.0	0.0			0.7	3.13	11.93
DEdeg	-48.79	16.15	-77.89	-17.89	105865176	0	100.0	0.0			-69.87	-48.77	-26.77
eDEdeg	5.53	5.99	0.02	138.96	105865176	0	100.0	0.0			0.77	3.44	13.06
pmRA	-1.08	4.85	-1172.19	6491.22	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			-5.15	-1.29	2.57
epmRA	0.42	0.45	0.01	3.43	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			0.05	0.27	1.0
pmDE	2.79	5.66	-5708.61	1707.7	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			-0.66	2.52	7.01
epmDE	0.46	0.48	0.01	3.75	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			0.06	0.3	1.1
pm	5.29	6.05	0.0	8644.32	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			1.62	3.95	9.85
epm	0.43	0.97	0.0	12.49	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			0.0	0.08	1.16
Plx	0.34	0.87	-54.47	272.16	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			-0.37	0.27	1.15
ePlx	0.38	0.36	0.01	5.19	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			0.05	0.26	0.87
distance	3486.63	2029.07	3.67	67932.2	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			1182.1	3239.27	5961.01
edistance	1507.71	1094.44	0.0	44129.2	92765752	13099424	87.63	12.37			153.82	1405.72	2854.49
posEpoch			1991.25	2028.3	105865176	0	100.0	0.0					
refEpoch			1991.25	2016.0	105865176	0	100.0	0.0					

LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 Release Notes (for PIC users)

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Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
posPropFlag			0	2	105865176	0	100.0	0.0					
PlatoMagNCAM	18.91	1.65	-0.71	22.56	105539562	325614	99.69	0.31			16.66	19.31	20.55
ePlatoMagNCAM	0.09	0.12	0.0	2.57	105539562	325614	99.69	0.31			0.01	0.04	0.27
PlatoMagFCAMb	19.45	1.72	-0.64	24.92	105539562	325614	99.69	0.31			17.1	19.9	21.09
ePlatoMagFCAMb	0.21	0.38	0.0	3.43	105539562	325614	99.69	0.31			0.02	0.08	0.36
PlatoMagFCAMr	18.47	1.65	-0.79	22.21	105539562	325614	99.69	0.31			16.24	18.82	20.18
ePlatoMagFCAMr	0.14	0.24	0.0	2.22	105539562	325614	99.69	0.31			0.01	0.06	0.24
caseFlag			1	27	105865176	0	100.0	0.0					
Gmag	19.24	1.65	1.96	22.92	105728283	136893	99.87	0.13			16.99	19.66	20.86
eGmag	0.01	0.01	0.0	0.39	105728283	136893	99.87	0.13			0.0	0.0	0.02
BPmag	19.71	1.69	2.35	25.32	98379105	7486071	92.93	7.07			17.41	20.17	21.33
eBPmag	0.09	0.09	0.0	3.09	98379105	7486071	92.93	7.07			0.01	0.06	0.19
RPmag	18.4	1.66	1.54	24.7	98630722	7234454	93.17	6.83			16.15	18.74	20.1
eRPmag	0.05	0.07	0.0	3.09	98630721	7234455	93.17	6.83			0.0	0.03	0.13
Hpmag	6.19	3.82	-0.55	12.51	22	105865154	0.0	100.0			1.72	7.53	9.74
eHpmag	0.01	0.04	0.0	0.17	22	105865154	0.0	100.0			0.0	0.0	0.01
BTmag	7.9	4.38	-0.42	14.18	23	105865153	0.0	100.0			1.65	10.02	12.93
eBTmag	0.07	0.11	0.01	0.36	23	105865153	0.0	100.0			0.01	0.03	0.28
VTmag	6.95	4.27	-0.61	13.04	24	105865152	0.0	100.0			1.82	8.74	11.99
eVTmag	0.04	0.07	0.0	0.28	24	105865152	0.0	100.0			0.0	0.02	0.13

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Name	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	nValid	nNull	%nValid	%nNull	bitmaskValid	bitmaskEmpty	Q10	Median	Q90
NSSFlag									440434	105424742			
qualityFlag									105865161	15			
contaminantStatusFlag									0	105865176			
isAlsoTargetFlag			0	1	105865176	0	100.0	0.0					

The column **posPropFlag** is a flag indicating if and how the positions of the contaminants were propagated. The occurrences of the values of column posPropFlag are listed in the following table:

posPropFlag value	number of contaminants
0	13099424
1	92765731
2	21

The column **isAlsoTargetFlag** is a flag indicating if a contaminant is also a target. The occurrences of the values of column isAlsoTargetFlag are listed in the following table:

isAlsoTargetFlag value	number of contaminants
0	105575923
1	289253

The column **caseFlag** is an integer flag which gives the basic information on the inputs used to calculate the PLATO magnitudes for the targets and the contaminants in both FCAM and NCAM. In the LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1 table not all possible caseFlag values are present. In the following table we include the occurrences for each of the caseFlag values present in the table:

caseFlag value	number of contaminants
1	67779564
2	6287422
3	5642701
4	4720423
5	3781038
6	17988
7	4479452
10	1
12	2
13	6
20	57155
21	10050339
22	2969356
27	79729

The column **NSSflag** is a bitmask indicating the presence of binary/multiple stellar system (NSS = non-single star). The occurrences of the possible bits in column NSSflag are listed in the following table:

NSSflag bit	number of contaminants
$000000_2 = 0$	105424742
$000001_2 = 1$	440434
$000010_2 = 2$	223058
$000100_2 = 4$	148116
$001000_2 = 8$	50814

NSSflag bit	number of contaminants
010000 ₂ = 16	28102

The column **qualityFlag** is a bitmask containing indicators for issues in Gaia astrometry and photometry. The occurrences of the possible bits in column qualityFlag are listed in the following table:

qualityFlag bit	number of contaminants
000000000 ₂ = 0	15
000000001 ₂ = 1	0
000000010 ₂ = 2	14517934
000000100 ₂ = 4	1968646
000001000 ₂ = 8	9725005
000010000 ₂ = 16	10096579
000100000 ₂ = 32	14638633
001000000 ₂ = 64	16800600
001000000 ₂ = 128	5366
010000000 ₂ = 256	827
100000000 ₂ = 512	66683070

5.2 LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv histograms

6. LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1 table contains, for each object in the LOPS2PICcontaminant2.2.0.1 table, the source identifiers from catalogues and/or surveys relevant for the PIC implementation.

This additional sourceId table is meant to include only the identifiers from catalogues that were used for the selection and/or characterisation of a given source.

When information from a given catalogue was not used for characterising a source, additional sourceIds are not included.

6.1 LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv statistics

The relevant statistics for all the columns in LOPS2PICcontaminantAdditionalSourceId2.2.0.1 table are listed in the following table:

name	nValid	%nValid	nNull	%nNull
PICcontaminantId	105865176	100.0	0	0.0
GaiaSourceId	105865161	100.0	15	0.0
Hipparcos2SourceId	20	0.0	105865156	100.0
HipparcosDMSourceId	1	0.0	105865175	100.0
Tycho2TDSCmergeSourceId	6	0.0	105865170	100.0

7. LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1 table contains a subsample of the columns included in LOPS2EPICtarget2.2.0.1 table.

For both the statistics and the histograms for the EPICtarget columns, please see Section 3.

8. LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1-t-fg-c-scv

The LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1 table contains a subsample of the columns included in LOPS2EPICcontaminant2.2.0.1 table.

For both the statistics and the histograms for the EPICcontaminant columns, please see Section 5.

9. LOPS2PIC2.2.0.1 contributors

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fgPIC implementation	C. Jiang, R. Heller, P.M. Marrese, S. Marinoni, M. Montalto
cPIC implementation	C. Jiang, R. Heller, P.M. Marrese, S. Marinoni, M. Montalto
scvPIC implementation	C. Jiang, R. Heller, S. Marinoni, P.M. Marrese, M. Montalto, J. Cabrera, C. Paproth, A. Börner

Contribution	Contributors
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EPIC tables definition	L. O'Rourke

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The science calibration and verification PLATO Input Catalog (scvPIC)

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